

2 Poems by Gianpiero Actis

Water is alive

Like a fickle spirit
Water modulates its voice and changes.
Thunder roars in the ravine
Deafening silence in the lake

Relentless movement of the tides
Crash of waves on the cliffs

Sound of a fierce hurricane
Tinkling of a delicate rain

Rhythmic beat of the drop
Traucherous crunch of ice

Crackling and icy hail
Silent and timid dew

Eternally guiding us to its knowledge.

Magic of lost time

*“Nostalgia ... the longing for yet another strange land,
grew especially strong in spring.”*
Vladimir Nabokov, *Mary*

I entered a shady path
On the edge primroses and violets whispered
Memories of bygone times.

In the distance a glimpse of the lake
Reflected restless clouds.

The lights and shadows chased each other
- almost a kids' game -

Silver fishes
Seemed to draw on the surface
Circles expanding
as in gentle breaths -

And suddenly
The magic of lost time
was here again.

Bio:

Gianpiero Actis (Italy)- artist and poet. He is one of the co-founders (with Aeronwy Thomas - daughter Dylan Thomas) of the artistic-literary movement "Immagine & Poesia". He often creates his artworks as *responses* to the poems of different authors. His success in the solo exhibition "Sguardi d'Artista" at the Promotrice delle Belle Arti in Turin opened a new way to pay homage to the "Eyes in Art" of internationally renowned artists

He has recently approached poetry with some creative writing compositions.

<https://gianpieroactis.jimdofree.com/>